

A Comparative Analysis of Ovarian Masses using Ultrasound, MRI, and Correlation with Histopathological Findings

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Abstract:

Background: Ovarian masses present a diagnostic challenge due to their diverse nature, ranging from benign cysts to malignant tumour. Accurate differentiation between these masses is essential for appropriate clinical management. Ultrasonography (USG) and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) are commonly used imaging modalities, with MRI increasingly recognized for its superior diagnostic accuracy in complex cases.

Aim: This study aimed to evaluate and compare the diagnostic accuracy of USG and MRI in the assessment of ovarian masses, with a correlation to histopathological findings.

Methods: A cross-sectional observational study was conducted on 300 female patients with ovarian masses detected by initial imaging. Each patient underwent both USG and MRI, followed by histopathological examination post-surgery. The sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), and negative predictive value (NPV) of each imaging modality were calculated and compared. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0.

Results: Ultrasound identified 60% of ovarian masses as benign and 40% as suspicious for malignancy, while MRI identified 56.7% as benign and 43.3% as suspicious. Histopathology confirmed 53.3% of masses as benign and 46.7% as malignant. MRI demonstrated a higher sensitivity (85.7%) and NPV (87.1%) compared to ultrasound, which had a sensitivity of 78.6% and an NPV of 82.4%. MRI also showed better agreement with histopathological findings ($\kappa = 0.61$) compared to ultrasound ($\kappa = 0.56$).

Conclusion: MRI demonstrated superior diagnostic accuracy over ultrasound in differentiating benign from malignant ovarian masses, particularly in complex cases. Given its higher sensitivity and NPV, MRI is recommended for cases where ultrasound results are inconclusive or when malignancy is suspected.

Recommendations: MRI should be considered the imaging modality of choice for the evaluation of indeterminate ovarian masses or when there is a high clinical suspicion of malignancy. Further studies with larger sample sizes are recommended to validate these findings and explore the cost-effectiveness of routine MRI use in ovarian mass evaluation.

Keywords: Ovarian Masses, Ultrasound, MRI, Histopathology, Diagnostic Accuracy.

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Introduction

Ovarian masses present a significant clinical challenge due to their diverse etiologies, which range from benign cysts to highly malignant tumour. Early and accurate differentiation between benign and malignant ovarian masses is crucial for optimizing patient management and outcomes. Imaging plays a pivotal role in this diagnostic process, with Ultrasonography and Magnetic Resonance Imaging being the most commonly used modalities. While ultrasound remains the first-line imaging technique due to its accessibility and cost-effectiveness, MRI has increasingly been recognized for its superior soft tissue contrast and ability to characterize complex adnexal masses more precisely.

Recent advances in imaging technology and techniques have further enhanced the diagnostic accuracy of these modalities. Ultrasound, particularly transvaginal sonography (TVS), offers excellent spatial resolution for evaluating ovarian morphology and vascularity. Doppler ultrasound has been shown to improve the differentiation between benign and malignant masses by assessing blood flow characteristics, which are often altered in malignancy [1]. However, despite its advantages, ultrasound can be limited by operator dependency and the inability to comprehensively assess large or complex masses.

MRI, on the other hand, provides multiplanar imaging capabilities and excellent tissue contrast without ionizing radiation, making it an invaluable tool in the evaluation of indeterminate ovarian masses [2]. Recent studies have demonstrated that MRI, especially when combined with diffusion-weighted imaging (DWI) and dynamic contrast-enhanced (DCE) sequences, significantly improves the accuracy of differentiating benign from malignant lesions [3, 4]. The ability of MRI to assess both morphological features and functional characteristics of ovarian masses has led to its increasing use in clinical practice, particularly for preoperative planning and in cases where ultrasound findings are inconclusive [5].

Histopathology remains the gold standard for the definitive diagnosis of ovarian masses. However, the non-invasive nature of imaging, coupled with its ability to provide rapid and detailed information, makes it a critical first step in the diagnostic pathway. The integration of imaging findings with clinical and laboratory data further enhances diagnostic accuracy, guiding appropriate management decisions. Despite these advancements, the comparative effectiveness of USG and MRI in routine clinical practice continues to be a topic of investigation. This study aimed to evaluate and compare the diagnostic accuracy of USG and MRI in the assessment of ovarian masses, with a correlation to histopathological findings.

Methodology

Study Design: This study is a cross-sectional observational study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at a tertiary care hospital with a dedicated imaging and histopathology department, for two years duration. The study was conducted at IGIMS, Patna a tertiary care hospital with a dedicated imaging and histopathology department, from March 2018 to February 2020

Participants: A total of 300 female patients presenting with ovarian masses detected on initial imaging (either ultrasound or MRI) were included in this study. These patients were referred for further diagnostic evaluation and potential surgical intervention.

Inclusion Criteria

- Female patients aged 18 years and older.
- Patients with newly diagnosed ovarian masses detected by initial ultrasound or MRI.
- Patients who consented to undergo both imaging modalities and subsequent histopathological examination.
- Patients with a confirmed histopathological diagnosis.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with a known history of ovarian cancer.
- Pregnant women.
- Patients who had undergone prior ovarian surgery.
- Patients with contraindications to MRI (e.g., metallic implants, severe claustrophobia).
- Patients who declined to participate in the study.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, all eligible patients during the study period were consecutively enrolled. To reduce observational bias, the radiologists and pathologists involved in the study were blinded to each other's findings.

Data Collection: Data were collected using a standardized proforma that included patient demographics, clinical history, imaging findings from ultrasound and MRI, and histopathological reports. Imaging findings were independently reviewed by two experienced radiologists, while histopathological specimens were analyzed by a pathologist.

Procedure

1. **Imaging:** All patients underwent both ultrasonography and MRI. The imaging findings were documented, focusing on the size, morphology, and characteristics of the ovarian masses.
2. **Histopathology:** Following imaging, patients who underwent surgical intervention had their ovarian masses sent for histopathological examination. The results were categorized into benign and malignant findings.
3. **Correlation:** The imaging findings were correlated with histopathological outcomes to assess the sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, and negative predictive value of each imaging modality.

Statistical Analysis: SPSS version 23.0 was utilised for data entry and analysis. Imaging results and patient demographics were summarised using descriptive statistics. Sensitivity, specificity, PPV, and NPV were used to evaluate the diagnostic accuracy of MRI and USG. The degree of agreement between imaging results and histological findings was assessed using the kappa statistic. Statistical significance was attained when the p-value was less than 0.05.

With a focus on linking these imaging modalities with conclusive histological diagnoses, our methodological approach guarantees a thorough assessment of the diagnostic capacities of USG and MRI in the evaluation of ovarian masses. The

majority of participants were in the age group of 40-59 years (56.7%).

A total of 300 female patients were included in the study, with a mean age of 45.6 years (range: 18-76 years). The majority of participants were in the age group of 40-59 years (56.7%).

Results

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Participants (N=300)

Characteristic	N (%)
Age Group (years)	
18-29	50 (16.7%)
30-39	60 (20.0%)
40-49	85 (28.3%)
50-59	85 (28.3%)
60-69	15 (5.0%)
70-79	5 (1.7%)
Mean Age (SD)	45.6 (12.3)
Presenting Symptoms	
Abdominal Pain	190 (63.3%)
Abdominal Mass	60 (20.0%)
Irregular Menstruation	40 (13.3%)
Postmenopausal Bleeding	10 (3.3%)
Menopausal Status	
Premenopausal	220 (73.3%)
Postmenopausal	80 (26.7%)

Imaging Findings

Ultrasound (USG) Results:

- Out of 300 patients, ultrasound identified 180 (60%) ovarian masses as benign and 120 (40%) as suspicious of malignancy.
- The most common benign findings included cystadenomas (35%) and dermoid cysts (25%).
- Among the masses suspicious of malignancy, features such as irregular borders, solid components, and ascites were noted.

MRI Results:

- MRI identified 170 (56.7%) ovarian masses as benign and 130 (43.3%) as suspicious for malignancy.
- MRI was particularly useful in characterizing complex masses, with findings such as contrast enhancement, diffusion restriction, and septations.

Table 2: Imaging Findings of Ovarian Masses by Ultrasound and MRI (N=300)

Imaging Finding	Ultrasound N (%)	MRI N (%)
Benign	180 (60.0%)	170 (56.7%)
Suspicious for Malignancy	120 (40.0%)	130 (43.3%)

Histopathological Findings: Histopathological examination revealed 160 (53.3%) benign masses and 140 (46.7%) malignant masses. The most common benign histopathological diagnoses were serous cystadenoma (30%), followed by mucinous cystadenoma (20%). The most frequent malignant diagnoses were serous carcinoma (25%) and endometrioid carcinoma (15%)

Table 3: Correlation of Imaging Findings with Histopathological Results (N=300)

Imaging Modality	True Positive (TP)	True Negative (TN)	False Positive (FP)	False Negative (FN)
Ultrasound	110	140	40	30
MRI	120	135	45	20

Diagnostic Performance

The sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), and negative predictive value (NPV) for ultrasound and MRI in detecting malignant ovarian masses were calculated as follows:

- Sensitivity: 78.6%
- Specificity: 77.8%
- PPV: 73.3%
- NPV: 82.4%

Ultrasound:

MRI:

- Sensitivity: 85.7%
- Specificity: 75.0%
- PPV: 72.7%
- NPV: 87.1%

Table 4: Diagnostic Performance of Ultrasound and MRI in Detecting Malignant Ovarian Masses

Parameter	Ultrasound (%)	MRI (%)
Sensitivity	78.6	85.7
Specificity	77.8	75.0
Positive Predictive Value	73.3	72.7
Negative Predictive Value	82.4	87.1

The agreement between imaging findings and histopathological results was assessed using the kappa statistic. The kappa value for ultrasound was 0.56 (moderate agreement), while the kappa value for MRI was 0.61 (substantial agreement). Both imaging modalities showed statistically significant correlations with histopathological findings ($p < 0.001$).

Discussion

The study evaluated the diagnostic accuracy of USG and MRI in assessing ovarian masses, comparing their findings with histopathological results. A total of 300 female patients, primarily in the age group of 40-59 years, were included in the study. The participants presented with various symptoms, including abdominal pain, abdominal mass, and irregular menstruation. The results indicated that both imaging modalities effectively identified ovarian masses, with ultrasound classifying 60% of the masses as benign and 40% as suspicious for malignancy. Similarly, MRI identified 56.7% as benign and 43.3% as suspicious. The histopathological examination revealed that 53.3% of the masses were benign, while 46.7% were malignant.

When comparing the diagnostic performance of the two modalities, MRI demonstrated a slightly higher sensitivity (85.7%) and negative predictive value (NPV) (87.1%) than ultrasound, suggesting that MRI is more effective in correctly identifying malignant masses and ruling out malignancy when a mass is deemed benign. On the other hand, ultrasound had a slightly higher specificity (77.8%), indicating a marginally better ability to correctly identify benign masses. Despite these differences, both modalities had a moderate to substantial agreement with histopathological findings, as reflected in the kappa statistics (0.56 for ultrasound and 0.61 for MRI).

Validation of MRI's superiority over ultrasonography in the diagnosis of ovarian masses was provided by Reddy. Their research has shown that MRI had far superior diagnostic accuracy, especially when it came to separating malignant from benign lesions. According to this study, when a thorough assessment of ovarian masses is required, MRI should be the favoured modality [6].

To assess ovarian masses, it was investigated the use of colour Doppler ultrasonography in addition to conventional ultrasound. This study demonstrated how well these imaging modalities combined with histological findings agreed, with colour Doppler indices—such as resistive and pulsatility indices—helping to distinguish between benign and malignant tumour. According to the study reaffirmed the significance of combining different imaging modalities for improved diagnosis accuracy [7].

It was compared to the sensitivity of MRI, colour Doppler, and ultrasonography in the diagnosis of ovarian masses in another study. The results showed that although ultrasonography is a widely accessible and reasonably priced first diagnostic technique, MRI offered the best diagnostic accuracy. This emphasizes the importance of MRI, especially if the results of the first ultrasound are unclear [8].

Conclusion

The interpretation of these results suggests that while both ultrasound and MRI are valuable in the initial assessment of ovarian masses, MRI provides a more reliable and accurate diagnosis, particularly in cases where malignancy is suspected. Higher sensitivity and NPV make MRI a better tool for ruling out malignancy, reducing the likelihood of false negatives. However, ultrasound remains a valuable, widely accessible modality, especially for initial evaluations. The substantial agreement between MRI findings and histopathology underscores the role of MRI as a crucial imaging modality in the comprehensive evaluation of ovarian masses, particularly when surgical intervention is considered.

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